

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

4 Temperate North Pacific Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

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With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Zm *Zostera marina*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
 - Leaf tip smoothly rounded
 - Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
 - 2 bundles of roots per node
 - Monoecious

Flowering Parts

Seedling

Seed

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zj *Nanozostera japonica*

Bioregion
4

- Key**
- Notched rounded leaf tip
 - Narrow leaf blades (2-5 mm)
 - Leaves 7-30 cm long
 - Monoecious
 - Intertidal - shallow subtidal

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pr *Phyllospadix serrulatus*

Bioregion
4

Attached to rocks

Key

- Flat leaves to 130 cm
- Rounded/flattened tip
- Serrated leaf edges
- 5-7 leaf veins
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Ps *Phyllospadix scouleri*

Bioregion
4

Attached to rocks

- Key
- Leaves, bi-convex cross-section, to 200cm
 - Rounded/flattened/notched tip
 - Rhizome internodes with yellow/gray fibers
 - 3 leaf veins
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pt *Phyllospadix torreyi*

Bioregion

4

Attached to rocks

Key

- Rolled leaves to 200cm
- Rounded slightly notched tip
- 3 leaf veins
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Za *Zostera asiatica*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 150 cm
- Flattened notched tip
- Thick rhizome
- Seeds 3-5mm brown and smooth
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Near Threatened

Zs *Zostera caespitosa*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 70 cm with rounded notched tip
- Flowering shoot to 60 cm with many branches
- Rhizome robust with short internodes
- Persistent sheath giving a tufted appearance
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Z1 *Zostera caulescens*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves 10-100cm with a short sharp tip
- Flowering shoot to 7m with many branches
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded with central point
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Near Threatened

Zf *Zostera pacifica*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- 2 bundles of roots per node
- Monoecious
- Confused with Za and Zm in N America

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Pi *Phyllospadix iwatensis*

Attached to rocks

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 150cm with rounded tip
- Yellowish/brown rhizome
- 5 leaf veins
- Dioecious

www.inaturalist.org/taxa

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Pj *Phyllospadix japonicus*

Bioregion

4

Attached to rocks

Key

- Flat leaves to 100cm with rounded tip
- Black rhizome internode fibers
- 3 leaf veins
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: **Endangered**

Roofs in Chinese village

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Bioregion
4

- Key**
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tip usually 2 points
 - Leaves 2-22 cm long
 - Rhizome whitish
 - Dioecious
 - Depth -1 to 20 m
 - Sometimes leaves appear red or black

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tapers to tip
 - Leaves 4-22 cm long
 - Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Paddle-shaped leaf
 - Leaf hairs on both side
 - Leaf margins serrated
 - Leaves 1-4 cm long
 - Monoecious
 - Depth 0-30 m

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

HK *Halophila nipponica*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Paddle-shaped leaves, no hairs
 - Leaf margins smooth
 - Leaves 1-5cm long
 - Depth 0-30 m

Fig. 2. Morphology of *Halophila nipponica* off the southern coast of Korea. (A) Male flower (arrow) with three purple stamens. (B) Female flower with ovoid ovary and three styles. (C) Leaf blade with 12 pairs of cross-veins. (D) An ovoid fruit. (E) Seed. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of the article.)

Extinction Risk: Data Deficient

From Jeong Bae Kim et al 2009

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